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EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON THE EFFECT OF THE WAKE TOPOLOGY ON THE PRESSURE LOSS IN A HIGH PRESSURE TURBINE CASCADE

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ABSTRACT

An experimental study on the influence of the wake traverse position on the integral pressure loss coefficients in a transonic high-pressure turbine cascade is presented. Realistic operating points for turbomachinery with Mach numbers ranging from $Ma_{2th} = 0.94 - 1.10$ at a constant exit Reynolds number of $Re_{2th} = 1,200,000$ are examined. The total pressure fields are estimated from planar Particle Image Velocimetry (PIV) measurements by applying a pressure reconstruction approach. The data is validated against five-hole probe measurements showing very good agreement. The findings demonstrate that the wake topology is influenced by the surrounding free-stream velocity, leading to a repetitive pattern of constrictions and dilations. The mixed-out loss coefficient was found to be the most sensitive to the axial traverse position. The evolution of the loss coefficient in the regarded near wake region is not exclusively dependent on the shape of the wake.

Keywords: Flow total pressure loss, pressure from PIV, transonic turbine

NOMENCLATURE

Abbreviations

2D2C 2 dimensional- 2 components
B2B blade-to-blade
FoV Field of View
HGK High-speed Cascade Wind Tunnel
MWP Miniaturized Wedge Probe
PIV Particle Image Velocimetry
PS Pressure Side
RTE Round Trailing Edge
SS Suction Side
TE Trailing Edge

Symbols

β pitch angle
c chord length
 γ isentropic coefficient
 Ma Mach number
p pitch
 π cooling air blowing ratio $\pi = \frac{P_{tc}}{P_{ref}}$
R determination coefficient
 Re Reynolds number
 Tu turbulence intensity
T temperature
V absolute velocity

- x horizontal coordinate
- y vertical coordinate
- ζ pressure loss coefficient

Subscripts

- 1 inlet plane
- 2 exit plane
- ax axial
- c cooling
- int integral
- is isentropic
- mo mixed-out
- norm normalized
- ref reference
- t total
- th theoretical

1 INTRODUCTION

The precise experimental quantification of the separate loss mechanisms in cascades is of fundamental importance for the development of efficient turbomachinery. One such loss parameter is the flow loss generated by dissipation due to wake mixing and skin friction as defined by Denton [1]. This definition includes loss caused by compression shocks, loss due to the development of the boundary layer, and loss generated in the base region of the trailing edge. The wake flow

downstream of cascades can be divided into three zones: the trailing edge region, the near-wake and the far-wake, compare Raj and Lakshminarayana [2]. The trailing edge region lasts up to 5% chord downstream of the trailing edge. It is characterized by high turbulence and intense mixing, leading to a rapid reduction of the wake velocity deficit and a rapid increase in the wake width. The near-wake region is located between 5 and 40% chord. Here, the velocity deficits are about as high as the free-stream velocity. Downstream of 40% the far-wake begins, which is defined by a small velocity deficit and an about constant wake width. This mixing continues until a fully mixed-out state is reached in a far distance from the trailing edge. Denton [1] states that with a control volume approach the wake decay rate is not important, as the details of the mixing process do not need to be known to correctly calculate the mixed-out loss. It suffices to accurately measure the conditions downstream of the trailing edge to predict the correct mixed-out loss. Based on this thesis, wake traverse measurements are usually conducted. In cascade flows, aerodynamic losses are derived from local flow quantities which are typically measured at a distance between 20 and 80% axial chord downstream of the cascade exit plane. Under the assumption of continuous mixing, the measured local inhomogeneous quantities are transferred into homogeneous quantities according to, e.g. Amecke [3]. The method proposed by Amecke is considered especially suitable for transonic flows as it is not restricted to sub- or supersonic flow, nor does it contain assumptions on the distribution of the static pressure. However, particularly in transonic flows, the wake mixing occurs in a complex flow field. It is influenced by the expansion area in the free-stream as well as shocks, which lead to local constrictions of the wake. An exemplary visualization of the wake shape that was experimentally measured with Particle Image Velocimetry (PIV) in the wake of a transonic turbine cascade is depicted in Fig. 1.

FIGURE 1. MACH NUMBER CONTOURS (PIV) SHOWING THE WAKE SHAPE AT EXIT MACH NUMBER $Ma_{2th} = 0.94$.

This study aims to quantify the impact of the position of the axial measurement plane on the mixed-out, mass-, and area-averaged integral total pressure loss. The investigation is carried out on a high-pressure turbine cascade operated under transonic conditions. In a previous study, Gohl et al. [4] have shown that the flow of the investigated linear cascade exhibits high unsteadiness. Acoustic waves originating at the trailing edge crucially affect the shock system. Complexity is added to the flow due to oscillating shocks. The flow field is examined via Particle Image Velocimetry (PIV), allowing a high spatial resolution of the wake and free-stream flow. The total pressure data of the exit flow field are obtained

via a pressure reconstruction schema, which includes a validation of the PIV data with classical pneumatic wake traverse measurements conducted with a five-hole pressure probe.

2 METHODOLOGIES

The experimental data was collected in the High-speed Cascade Wind Tunnel (HGK) of the Institute of Jet Propulsion. The main components of the wind tunnel are contained inside a pressure tank. Thus, an independent variation of the Mach and Reynolds number is possible, which enables investigations under engine-relevant operating conditions. For an extensive description of the test facility, see Niehuis and Bitter [5]. Figure 2 shows the experimental setup of the investigated linear cascade installed in the wind tunnel measurement section. The investigated high-pressure turbine profile has two film cooling rows, one of which is located on the suction side upstream of the throat, and the second row is located on the pressure side close to the trailing edge. In this study, the conventional round trailing edge shape was studied. More information on the profile parameters is available in Gohl et al. [4].

A planar 2D2C-PIV setup was installed to capture the blade-to-blade (B2B) wake flow at midspan. The resulting Field of View (FoV) is indicated in Fig. 2, highlighted in pink. The Nd:YAG double pulse laser INNOLAS Spotlight 1000 was used to form the light sheet. The laser is placed outside of the pressure chamber, and the light is guided

FIGURE 2. SKETCH OF THE HGK MEASUREMENT SECTION WITH THE EXAMINED HIGH PRESSURE TURBINE CASCADE BUILT IN (NOT TO SCALE).

into the measurement section using multiple mirrors. Two PIVTEC seeding generators are used to produce DEHS seeding particles of approximately 1 μm diameter into two seeding volumes also placed outside of the wind tunnel pressure chamber. The use of two separate seeders allows seeding both the main flow and the cooling air flow. The seeding is soaked into the flow due to the lower pressure in the wind tunnel. As camera, the LaVision Imager sCMOS camera with a resolution of 2560 X 2160 px and a frame rate of 15 fps was utilized. Around 5,500 images were recorded for each operation point, corresponding to a recording time close to 6 min. The PIV data was evaluated with the software DaVis 10.2 including the pressure from PIV functions. Following multiple preprocessing steps, a multi-pass PIV algorithm with an interrogation window size of 48 x 48 px and 75% overlap in combination with subpixel window shift was applied. The resulting spatial resolution is one velocity vector per about 0.7 mm. To compare the PIV velocity field with pressure probe measurements, the local Mach number was calculated from the absolute velocity as follows:

$$Ma = \sqrt{\frac{V^2}{\gamma RT_{t1} - \frac{\gamma-1}{2} \cdot V^2}} \quad (1)$$

The ensemble averaged velocity fields were then transformed into time-averaged pressure fields. For a full description of the principle for pressure reconstruction via PIV, see e.g. van Oudheusden [6] or Van der Kindere et al. [7]. Calculating the time-averaged pressure fields from the velocity data consists of two steps. To begin with, the mean pressure gradients are computed using the Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equation. Secondly, the divergence of the acquired pressure gradient field is formed resulting in the Poisson equation which then needs to be solved. To solve the differential equation and gain an absolute pressure field, at least one pressure must be predefined. As a Dirichlet boundary condition, the static average pressure of the entire FoV was set close to the pressure vessel. Note that the pressure field estimation is carried out for incompressible fluid, i.e. the density and viscosity are assumed constant.

Wake traverses were conducted with a miniaturized wedge probe (MWP), which is a five-hole probe and is specifically designed for transonic flow measurements, see Börner and Niehuis [8]. The MWP is calibrated for a Mach number range of 0.5 to 1.6 and pitch angles ranging between ±16°. The calibration was performed at an ambient pressure of 120 hPa. Wake traverses were

conducted along 5% and about 30% axial chord covering the entire pitch-wise distance visible in the FoV. Probe data were used to validate and calibrate the PIV pressure data. The pressure reconstruction approach applied here and its validation are described in detail in Bitter and Kožulović [9].

The local and integral pressure loss coefficient is calculated as defined:

$$\zeta = \frac{p_{t1} - p_{t2}}{p_{t1} - p_2} \quad (2)$$

The most simple way to calculate the integral exit quantities is area-averaging. Alternatively, the integral exit quantities can be acquired by applying mass-averaging and thus taking the decreased mass flow in the wake into account. The mass flow density is calculated with the local axial velocity as defined:

$$c_{ax}(y) = Ma_2(y) \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\gamma RT_{t1}}{1 + \frac{\gamma-1}{2} Ma_2(y)^2}} \cdot \sin\beta_2(y) \quad (3)$$

Where y denotes the pitchwise coordinate. The local static density is derived from isentropic relations. The integral mixed-out pressure is calculated following the approach described by Amecke [10] using local measurements from one pitch of the total pressure $p_{t2}(y)$, static pressure $p_2(y)$, and pitch angle $\beta_2(y)$. A control volume is built around the plane of interest for which mass, momentum, and energy balances are formulated. Under the assumption of a uniform total temperature distribution and adiabatic flow, three pitchwise integrals I_1 , I_2 and I_3 are calculated from weighted combinations of $p_{t2}(y)$, $p_2(y)$, $\sin(\beta_2(y))$ and $\cos(\beta_2(y))$. The integrals are used to solve the balance equations and, thus, total pressure $p_{t2,mo}$, static pressure $p_{2,mo}$, and pitch angle $\beta_{2,mo}$ for the mixed-out state are obtained.

The operating points inspected are summarized in Table 1. In the entire configuration, the ambient pressure is the only pressure measured with an absolute pressure

TABLE 1. TEST CONDITIONS.

Ma_{2th}	Re_{2th}	$\pi_{c,SS}$	$\pi_{c,TE}$	Tu_1	T_{t1}
0.94	1.2×10^6	2.10	1.64	3 %	303.15 K
1.00	1.2×10^6	2.10	1.64	3 %	303.15 K
1.10	1.2×10^6	2.10	1.64	3 %	303.15 K

transducer. The used Mensor CPG2500 pressure transducer has an pressure range of 552 - 1,172 hPa and the precision is 0.01% of the full-scale range. All other pressures are measured using differential pressure transducers. Wake traverse measurements were recorded by the 9116 pressure scanner from PSI pressure System with an operating range of ± 25 hPa to ± 345 hPa and an uncertainty of 0.15% and 0.05% of the full-scale range (absolute: 4 and 17 Pa), respectively. All pressure data were sampled with a frequency of 20 Hz and averaged over a period of 10 s. The inlet total temperature T_{t1} is averaged from four pt100 with a precision of ± 0.3 K. The measurement uncertainty for PIV depends on systematic and random errors; compare Raffel et al. [11]. The systematic error sources are the setup, data acquisition, and evaluation process, and their quantification is limited. The random error of the experiment depends on statistics. For this study, the maximum uncertainty of the absolute velocity in the passage flow is $V_{err} = 0.25$ m/s and in the wake close to the trailing edge is $V_{err} = 1$ m/s. Together with the uncertainty of the total temperature, the resulting error for the Mach number 0.02 and 0.08, respectively. The velocity flow angle uncertainty is estimated to be $\beta_{err} < 0.4^\circ$. The accuracy of the PIV pressure reconstruction is not provided by DaVis.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Wake topology at different exit Mach numbers

Wake flows are best characterized by the velocity deficit, therefore, the ensemble-averaged Mach number distribution at the three exit Mach numbers $Ma_{2th} = 0.94$ to 1.10 are depicted in Fig. 3. The illustrated Mach number fields are normalized to the maximum Mach number of each field. A detailed flow analysis can be found in Gohl et al. [12]. In this paper the focus is on the evolution of the wake. The flow direction is indicated by the arrow in the lower left corner and the trailing edge of the measurement blade is visible at the relative coordinates [1,0]. To highlight the wake shape, the wake envelope of the measurement blade is sketched by black contours. For $Ma_{2th} = 0.94$ (left), just downstream of the wake up to approximately 110% relative chord, the wake slightly widens. Furthermore, the dense accumulation of contours and the contour color drop indicate the rapid mixing of the flow. Contrary to the theory that the wake expands with growing distance from the trailing edge, at around 120% relative chord, a narrowing of the wake becomes visible, marked (I). The position of the constriction (I) correlates with the end of the expansion region from the neighboring PS passage. This expansion area is not limited by the wake but is also visible on the

FIGURE 3. B2B-VIEW OF THE NORMALIZED MACH NUMBER CONTOURS AT EXIT MACH NUMBERS $Ma_{2th} = 0.94$ (LEFT), $Ma_{2th} = 1.00$ (MIDDLE), AND $Ma_{2th} = 1.10$ (RIGHT). THE WAKE ENVELOPE OF THE MEASUREMENT BLADE IS SKETCHED BY THE BLACK LINE. THE MARKERS (I) AND (II) INDICATE CONSTRICTIONS AND DILATION OF THE WAKES, RESPECTIVELY.

wake SS. Downstream of this constriction, a widening of the wake can be detected once more, which has reached its maximum at around 135% relative chord, highlighted (II). Wake growth takes place in the deceleration region of the PS passage. High-speed Schlieren images visualize that in this region weak compression waves propagate upstream originating at the adjacent blade trailing edge, compare Gohl et al. [4]. The wake width maximum (II) is followed by another wake necking caused by the expansion area from the passage above the adjacent blade (not in the FoV anymore). Thus, it is assumed that the described pattern between the expansion i.e. constriction of the wake and deceleration regions i.e. expansion of the wake is repeated. The "breathing" shape of the wake is experimentally documented by e.g. Jagodzińska et al. [13] or Okada et al. [14]. The later authors present B2B PIV measurements for a low pressure turbine at $Ma_{2th} = 0.90$ and $Ma_{2th} = 0.95$ which depicted a similar wake shape.

When increasing the exit Mach number to $Ma_{2th} = 1.00$ (middle), the PS passage normal shock is clearly apparent by the concentration of the Mach contours as noted by the arrow. At around 130% relative axial chord, just upstream of the shock the wake constriction marked (I) can be observed. The constriction seems more pronounced than for $Ma_{2th} = 0.94$ as higher pressure gradients are present. The normal shock cuts through the wake upstream of

around 130% relative chord. The shock-wake interaction leads to a deceleration and a widening of the wake. Downstream of this knot (I), the wake width grows until approximately 140% relative chord (marked II) just before the end of the FoV, where the second narrowing of the wake starts.

Increasing the exit Mach number further, compare $Ma_{2th} = 1.10$ (right), the shock moves downstream to the adjacent blade trailing edge and is slightly inclined. As the expansion area covers most of the visible PS passage, the first constriction of the wake is placed at about 140% relative axial chord and is marked (I). Therefore, the wake shape between the measurement blade and position (I) is almost straight. The increased shock strength leads to a more intense interaction with the wake, which is visualized through the color drop of the contour. The widening following the deceleration by the shock seems sudden and restricted to a small region. It is less pronounced for $Ma_{2th} = 1.10$ than for the two lower exit Mach numbers.

3.2 Processing of the raw PIV pressure data

Following the approach suggested by Bitter and Kožulović [9], the raw PIV pressure data are fitted to conventional multi-hole pressure probe measurements.

FIGURE 4. FIT BETWEEN PIV AND CONVENTIONAL PROBE MEASUREMENTS BY MEANS OF THE TOTAL PRESSURE NORMALIZED TO THE INLET TOTAL PRESSURE. FOR INCREASED READABILITY THE DATA RANGES FOR $Ma_{2th} = 1.00$ AND $Ma_{2th} = 1.10$ ARE SHIFTED IN Y-DIRECTION.

This fit is necessary because the applied pressure reconstruction approach neglects compressibility effects. As the Mach numbers investigated are well within the transonic range and the flow fields exhibit signs of shock and unsteadiness this would lead to a major deviation. Therefore, a miniaturized wedge probe (MWP) was traversed at 105 and 130% axial chord to generate reference data, compare black dash-dotted lines in Fig. 3. The pitch measured with the MWP corresponds to the entire pitch visible in the FoV as indicated by the dash-dotted lines mentioned above. The extracted PIV data were fitted to the MWP data at these axial positions, totaling approximately 100 fitting points. Fig. 4 shows the correlation for the three Mach numbers investigated between the total pressure obtained from PIV and the total pressure measured by the MWP, both normalized to the inlet total pressure p_{t1} . For better readability, the plots for $Ma_{2th} = 1.00$ and $Ma_{2th} = 1.10$ are shifted in y-direction. A second-order polynomial fit proved to provide good and also stable results. Although high-order fits resulted in better statistics, they were less stable, especially when applied outside the fitted pressure range. The fits were evaluated using the coefficient of determination R^2 which is indicated for each operating point in the legend. For increasing Mach numbers, the goodness-of-fit increases as well. This is contrary to the observation made by Bitter and Kožulović [9]. One reason is that the largest scattering of fitting points is present for $Ma_{2th} = 0.94$.

3.3 Comparison of the MWP and fitted PIV data

A comparison of the fitted PIV data with the MWP wake traverses can be seen in Fig. 5 at 105% relative axial chord for all exit Mach numbers investigated. As the mixed-out pressure loss is impacted by the quantities of the local loss, Mach number and flow angle, normalized versions of these quantities are presented. PIV data is colored red, while the probe data is colored black. The axial position of 105% lies at the end of the trailing edge region as defined by Raj and Lakshminarayana [2] and was chosen mainly to cover the wide range of pressures in the field and is marked by the black dash-dotted line in Fig. 3. The wake in this region is dominated by

FIGURE 5. NORMALIZED LOSS (LEFT), MACH NUMBER (CENTER), AND EXIT FLOW ANGLE (RIGHT) MEASURED BY PIV (RED) AND PROBE (BLACK) AND EXTRACTED AT 105% CHORD FOR $Ma_{2th} = 0.94$, $Ma_{2th} = 1.00$, AND $Ma_{2th} = 1.10$.

high unsteadiness, strong shear stresses as a result of intense pressure gradients, and rapid mixing. When comparing the normalized local losses (left), in general, a very good agreement can be found between the PIV and MWP measurements, especially considering the flow characteristics in the trailing edge region. Minor deviations are visible in the free-stream between the two wakes for all exit Mach numbers. The free-stream loss measured by PIV increases with increasing pitch slightly, while the MWP displays a constant free-stream pressure loss. Also, for $Ma_{2th} = 1.00$ at about 70% relative pitch, compare red arrow, a small plateau, i.e. a loss increase, can be seen that is not reflected in the MWP measurement. The Mach number contours in Fig. 3 reveal that at this pitch position the shock crosses the measurement plane. For $Ma_{2th} = 1.10$ between 90 and 100% relative pitch, marked by the red arrow, PIV and MWP show different loss trends. The loss gradient is caused by the shock as can be seen in Fig. 3. While the MWP did not capture the shock loss at $Ma_{2th} = 1.00$, PIV predicts a loss decrease at $Ma_{2th} = 1.10$. Both measurement techniques seem to have difficulties in predicting the losses caused by shocks. The wake itself is quantitatively and spatially well captured, as PIV and MWP agree for all three exit Mach numbers. A slight overestimation of the wake PS is visible for PIV at $Ma_{2th} = 0.94$ and $Ma_{2th} = 1.00$. For $Ma_{2th} = 1.10$ the wake pressure losses are identical for PIV and MWP. When comparing the local normalized Mach numbers (center), it can be seen that for all three exit Mach numbers, lower local Mach number levels are found for PIV. This is consistent with observations made by Börner et al. [8]. They found a deviation between the PIV measurements and five-hole probe between 1 to 2.5% which is in agreement with the deviation in this study. Sanders et al. [15] investigated the blockage effect of probes by comparing the flow fields predicted with and without probe numerically. Contrary to the observations made here, they found that the probe measured Mach number is always below the undisturbed Mach number and amounts to up to $\Delta Ma = 3.2\%$. The profiles of the normalized local Mach number fit well between the two measurement techniques. Taking into account that pressure probes have a reduced sensitivity around Mach numbers close to unity which can last up to Mach 1.3, see Kost [16], and the additional blockage effect of the probe, this is a good confirmation of the probe measurements in this delicate flow regime. The normalized flow angle profiles are depicted on the right side of Fig. 5. Normalization was performed with the theoretical exit flow angle. The flow angle distributions of PIV and MWP match remarkably well and thus represent the same trends. A small offset between the two measurement techniques is apparent.

Throughout almost the entire extracted pitch PIV outputs lower flow angles than the MWP in the free-stream. This deviation is about 1 to 3% of β_{2th} (0.3 - 0.8°). Excluded from this statement are the wakes. On the wake PS, flow angles decline steeper for PIV than for the probe. This decrease is followed by a bump that is not captured by in the MWP measurements for all three exit Mach numbers. Okada et al. [14] report on much higher deviations between PIV and probe measurements. Especially in the wake, they found a significant overestimation of the flow angle gradients measured by the five-hole probe compared to PIV. The findings of Okada et al. [14] agree with Torre et al. [17].

In Fig. 6 the normalized local loss, Mach number, and flow angle at 130% axial chord are presented. The extraction position is highlighted by the dash-dotted black line in Fig. 3. This chord position is part of the near-wake zone. Mixing has progressed and the velocity gradients are flattening out, but there is still a pronounced velocity deficit present. Normalized local losses are visible on the left side of Fig. 6. In general, PIV and MWP loss data agree well. The free-stream losses are almost identical for PIV and MWP at all three exit Mach numbers. In the wake region the slight overestimation of the wake PS already seen at 105% axial chord is still present for $Ma_{2th} = 0.94$ and $Ma_{2th} = 1.00$. There is no indication of shock pressure losses for $Ma_{2th} = 1.00$ as at this chord position the shock is superimposed with the wake. For $Ma_{2th} = 1.10$ at about 90% relative pitch, cf. red arrow, the shock loss is captured by both measurement techniques, while PIV predicts a slightly stronger shock than the probe. The local Mach number profiles (center) are clearly flatter at 130% axial chord than at 105% axial chord. Apart from the offset already mentioned for 105% axial chord, the Mach number distributions of PIV and MWP are in very good agreement. Noteworthy is the velocity gradient caused by the shock and highlighted by the red arrow. This gradient is clearly more pronounced than the wake deficit, and again PIV and probe are in good agreement. Comparing the pitch angle profiles (right) of PIV and MWP the known offset, i.e. lower pitch angles for PIV are evident. Apart from that, the pitch angle distributions in the free-stream agree very well. The highest deviations are located at the PS of the wake. For $Ma_{2th} = 0.94$ and $Ma_{2th} = 1.00$ the deviations are qualitatively very similar and amount to about 8% β_{2th} . In case of $Ma_{2th} = 1.10$ the deviation is slightly smaller, but the MWP measurement in this region seems unstable, which might be due to the proximity to the shock.

$x_{ax}/c_{ax} = [10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40]\%$. All selected traverse positions are located within the near-wake region and are highlighted in Fig. 3 the by the white lines.

In Fig. 7 the loss coefficients for $Ma_{2th} = 0.94$ are depicted. For this exit Mach number, the most slender part of the wake is located around 125% relative chord, thereafter the wake expands and reaches its maximum width between 135% relative chord. For this exit Mach number, mass- and area-averaged loss coefficients are scarcely affected by the wake shape. The area-averaged loss increases marginally with increasing distance from the trailing edge, except for a small drop around 125%. The area-averaged loss varies in the observed chord range for about 5% of ζ_{ref} . The mass-averaged loss also decreases slightly around 125 to 130% relative chord and increases minimally but gradually thereafter. The mass-average loss coefficient varies around 6% of ζ_{ref} . As expected, the area-averaged loss is slightly higher than the mass-averaged loss for almost all inspected traverse positions except for 110% relative chord where both loss coefficients are about the same. The mixed-out loss is clearly affected by the choice of traverse position. The minimum is reached at 125% relative chord which matches the minimum wake width. Thereafter, the losses increase until 135% relative chord and drops again at 140% chord. This mixed-out loss increase would match with the expansion of the wake shape, but the drop at 140% chord seems too excessive and thus unrelated to the wake shape as the wake contraction starts further downstream. The observed delta in the mixed-out loss coefficient amounts to 20% ζ_{ref} .

FIGURE 6. NORMALIZED LOSS (LEFT), MACH NUMBER (CENTER), AND EXIT FLOW ANGLE (RIGHT) MEASURED BY PIV (RED) AND PROBE (BLACK) AND EXTRACTED AT 130% CHORD FOR $Ma_{2th} = 0.94$, $Ma_{2th} = 1.00$, AND $Ma_{2th} = 1.10$.

3.4 Influence the measurement plane position on the integral loss coefficient

Due to the wake topology, it is examined if the traverse position influences the integral pressure loss. The dependency of the normalized integral mixed-out loss calculated according to Amecke, the mass- and area-averaged loss coefficients on the wake traverse position for the three exit Mach numbers are described in the following. For normalization the integral mixed-out loss measured for $Ma_{2th} = 1.00$ at 130% relative chord was used as reference loss ζ_{ref} . The calculation was performed using the fitted PIV pressure data. Wake measurements of one pitch length were extracted at

FIGURE 7. DEPENDENCY OF NORMALIZED INTEGRAL MIXED-OUT, MASS- AND AREA-AVERAGED LOSS COEFFICIENTS ON THE AXIAL TRAVERSE POSITION FOR $Ma_{2th} = 0.94$.

FIGURE 8. DEPENDENCY OF NORMALIZED INTEGRAL MIXED-OUT, MASS- AND AREA-AVERAGED LOSS COEFFICIENTS ON THE AXIAL TRAVERSE POSITION FOR $Ma_{2th} = 1.00$.

Figure 8 illustrates the loss coefficients for $Ma_{2th} = 1.00$. The minimum wake width is located at 130% relative chord and the maximum width is approximately at 135 to 140% relative chord. Mass- and area averaged losses follow the same trend and increase until 125% relative chord and then decrease until 135% chord. This trend fits to the development of the wake width. The difference in the observed traverse position range is 10% and 15% ζ_{ref} for the mass- and area-averaged loss coefficients, respectively. The mixed-out loss reaches its maximum at 115% relative chord and decreases until 125% chord matching the evolution of the wake width. Upstream of 125% the mixed-out loss increase first and then drops again leading to a minimum at 140% relative chord. If the mixed-out loss would be correlated with the wake shape an increase in this area would be expected. The loss decrease is probably related to the position of the normal shock. The traverse positions upstream of 125% chord cross the shock either in the wake or on the opposite side of the wake where it is weaker. The mixed-out loss difference for the regarded traverse positions amounts to about 20% of ζ_{ref} .

The loss coefficients for the highest exit Mach number $Ma_{2th} = 1.10$ are shown in Fig 9. At this exit Mach number, the wake width is almost constant and increases around 135% chord suddenly. The area- and mass-averaged loss coefficients increase gradually about 18% and 11% of ζ_{ref} with increasing distance from the trailing edge until its maximum at 135% relative chord. The loss increase seems to be uncorrelated to the wake shape. The mixed-out loss spreads over 31% ζ_{ref} and has two significant drops at 115 and 135% relative chord.

FIGURE 9. DEPENDENCY OF NORMALIZED INTEGRAL MIXED-OUT, MASS- AND AREA-AVERAGED LOSS COEFFICIENTS ON THE AXIAL TRAVERSE POSITION FOR $Ma_{2th} = 1.10$.

Although the second drop agrees with the most slender wake position, the evolution of all three loss coefficients seems more complex and not only dependent on the wake shape.

With respect to one pitch at mid-span, it can be expected that the area-averaged loss coefficient is higher than the mass-averaged loss coefficient, as the wake represents the loss maximum and is damped by

FIGURE 10. NORMALIZED MASS-AVERAGED AND AREA-AVERAGED LOSS COEFFICIENT FOR 120 (BLACK) AND 130% CHORD (GREEN) AT $Ma_{2th} = 1.00$

the weighting with the mass flow density. Regarding $Ma_{2th} = 1.00$, this is not the case for traverse positions below 120% relative chord. For $Ma_{2th} = 1.10$, where the mass-averaged loss is higher than the area-averaged loss to about 125% axial chord. For these traverse positions, the velocity gradient over one pitch - free-stream PS to free-stream SS- is higher than the velocity gradient in the wake. Thus, close to the trailing edge, it can happen that the wake region is given a stronger weighting than the free-stream, leading to higher mass-averaged loss coefficients than area-averaged loss coefficients. Figure 10 illustrates the local mass flow density normalized by the averaged mass flow density, as well as the resulting normalized mass-averaged (solid lines) and area-averaged (dash-dotted lines) loss coefficient for 120% (black) and 130% chord (green) at $Ma_{2th} = 1.00$. Further downstream of the trailing edge, where the mixing process has progressed further, the gradient between the PS and SS free-stream is less pronounced. With increasing exit Mach numbers, it can be seen that the traverse position where the mass-averaged loss is higher than the area-averaged loss is increasing. This is due to the higher gradients in the free-stream for high exit Mach numbers.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Experimental data for a transonic high-pressure turbine cascade at turbomachinery representative Mach and Reynolds numbers are reported. The regarded operating points are three exit Mach numbers in the range between $Ma_{2th} = 0.94 - 1.10$ at a constant Reynolds number of $Re_{2th} = 1,200,000$. Total pressure flow fields are reconstructed from PIV velocity fields and validated against wake traverse data measured by a five-hole miniaturized wedge probe. For validation of the local loss, Mach number and exit flow angle distributions are examined. The fitted pressure fields show very good agreement with the probe measurements at both 105 and 130% axial chords for all inspected exit Mach numbers. The primary focus of the paper is to quantify the sensitivity of the axial position chosen for wake traverse measurements to the total pressure loss coefficients. Normalized Mach number contours clearly show that the wake shape is influenced by the surrounding free-stream. The wake appears to be more slender around expansion areas and widens in recompression regions of the free-stream. The resulting "breathing" shape of the wake was found to be most pronounced for $Ma_{2th} = 1.00$. For the highest exit Mach number the space between constriction and dilation is reduced as the shock becomes the dominating flow feature. Comparison of the area-, mass-averaged, and

mixed-out total pressure loss coefficients at wake traverse positions between 110 and 140% relative chord reveal that the mixed-out loss is the most sensitive of the three loss coefficients to the traverse position. The observed variance in the mixed-out loss can not be solely attributed to the wake shape and seems more complex. Area- and mass-averaged losses are found to be impacted in a similar way to the varying traverse positions and show small sensitivity to the wake shape. In general, it was found that with increasing exit Mach numbers, the variance of all three loss coefficients increases.

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